

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE ABILITIES

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Annotation

This article discusses today's current news about the pedagogical and psychological features of the development of creative abilities of students. Defects and problems are identified. Also in the article, the author gives general conclusions on the empirical research method he conducted.

Key words: creative ability, method, organization, free thought, problem, temperament, characteristic

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются современные новости о педагогических и психологических особенностях развития творческих способностей учащихся. Выявляются дефекты и проблемы. Также в статье автор дает общие выводы по проведенному им эмпирическому методу исследования.

Ключевые слова: творческие способности, метод, организация, свободомыслие, проблема, темперамент, характеристика.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada o'quvchilarning kreativ qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik xususiyatlari haqida olib borilgan bugungi kundagi dolzarb yangiliklar muhokama qilinadi. Kamchiliklar, muammolar aniqlanadi. Shuningdek maqolada muallif o'zi o'tkazgan imperik tadqiqot metodi bo'yicha umumiy xulosalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijodiy qobiliyat, metod, uyushqoqlik, erkin fikr, muammo, temperament, xususiyat

Introduction It is fast in the process of applying new methodologies suitable for their age clear results can be achieved at opportunities. More methodology for them the use of "mental attack", "competition" styles when choosing creative it gives even better results in the development of abilities. Children of the melancholic and phlegmatic type are less likely to have opposite effects paying attention, passive reacts. Children of this type the development of creative abilities is relevant in the face of today's science one of the problems. If we can find an effective solution to this problem, we will be able to surface and develop the existing abilities in them. Through this, the success of children of these two types increases significantly, it benefits society in every possible way. Creative to representatives of such a type when a method is selected for the development of abilities, it is mainly on them the use of the "Monarch" style in the primary period is that of the teacher taking sole control of the classroom, their intervention in the classroom it is necessary to provide astalik. From the exercises that develop on them formed peat hil handing out tasks, in the process of completing them Using the "mixed" method. In this method, the teacher and the student

activity is evenly distributed in the lesson. To the third stage with slow ascendancy, Switched to the " Republic " method. And in the process, management in the classroom is full-fledged into the hands of the reader. Teacher intervention decreases on its own. Independent thinking in the reader, the ability to make decisions is independent formed with the help of completed assignments. Step above as a result of the methods in the lesson in which the stage was carried out, students will have the development and cultivation of creative abilities gives an effective result. from this it can be seen that students develop their creative abilities only not only psychological, but also involved in self-pedagogical activity that's the process[1]. Even at the core of the concept of creative ability, it is precisely " creativity, step-by-step harvesters" take on importance. Pedagogical and educational development of students ' creative abilities psychological characteristics In the process of globalization today was in every field of education using both advanced methodologies to bring them to life, always life itself dictates to be renewed and developed. Training the main purpose of using modern technologies in the process in teaching students accessible and easy methods in mastering science. and pedagogical and psychological principles of their creative thinking asnosida consists of development. Several worlds in this direction schools have already formed. Including the American who first introduced the term " creative ability " to science research scientist J.P.Guilford (1959): "creative ability is a scientific theory. Without him, the learner cannot think independently, create news"[2]- said that, as well as continuing his theories again, proposed the creative ability to it is psychology that proves to be inextricably linked with pedagogy. In today's modern pedagogy, too, these two concepts are realized on increased research is a breeze. For example, the researcher S.A.Mednik "In the development of students' creative ability of subconscious signals the role as well as their reflective effects in cognitive training". if the scientific research on brogan, M.I.Smeshkin " Junior methods for determining and developing creative abilities in children from an early age" is doing research work on. This is also the case of Uzbek scientists scientific research in the direction brogan and those who are going are also trapped. Of These, K.J. Hakimova, L.T. Muhammedzhanova, R.S. Salimbekov, O.Rashidov.

Methods

Implementation in the direction of development of students ' creative abilities despite the ongoing research, its pedagogical and psychological creating clear and effective methodologies for the development of properties it remains one of today's current problems[3]. This the article also uses the Imperial research method that the author conducted himself using new, innovative ped to practice technology provides a number of opinions on, specific facts. Author kreative psychological as well as pedagogical features in the development of abilities one uses in the experiment in a separate way, concludes. In the following stage, this is two concepts are applied to practice in a single way, new methodologies through experience in students conducts test work. The psychological principle of developing students ' creative ability: The fact that each individ is mainly involved in one of the 4 important temperaments identified by people of science. Holerik, sangvenic, melancholic and.phlegmatic. Each of these concepts has its own in the personality creative approach shows a huge impact. Birth of children of the holerik and sanguine type owners of abilities, creators can also be said, in which the creative ability can be development will not be so difficult. They are an event by nature events can be influenced by reflection even without free, excessive attempts[4].

K. Rodgers (1944) creativity is a new solution to problems and something, the event understands how to identify new ways to express the state. Creativity with personality and intellectual properties compared Studies large of importance. Research on comparison with intellectual properties Dj. Performed by Guilford. Creativism is a personal characteristic of a person, whose self-esteem related to improvement and development. Creativity (lot., Eng. "create" - create, "creative" creator, creator) < BR > - describing the readiness of the individual to produce new ideas and creative ability, which is part of giftedness as an independent factor. Of an individual creativity in his thinking, communication, feelings, certain activities manifested in species[5].

In the development of creativity in children, it is necessary to pay attention to:

- 1) encourage a lot of questions to be asked by them and make this habit support;
- 2) encourage children's independence and to strengthen responsibility in them;
- 3) independent activities by children creating an opportunity to be organized;
- 4) focus on children's interests.

The following factors prevent the development of creativity in an individual:

- 1) taking oneself away from risk;
- 2) allowing rudeness in thinking and behavior;
- 3) lack of high appreciation of personality fantasy and imagination;
- 4) to be subject to others;
- 5) in any case, just thinking about the achievement.

Primary grade: methods for the development of creative abilities of animals and one of the important factors affecting the tools of teacher-student cooperation particular attention was paid to the fact that[6]. As you know, the educational process is two-fold organization from equal relationships of teachers and students, with character finds. The teacher who leads this process is the correct Organization of the educational process when clarifying some information on the subject under study addressing students as if they were seeking help further collaborative activities deepen. Making students a learner and educator read not only does it become a condition for the successful conduct of the teaching process, but also it is also an important condition for raising them as harmonious people in all respects. The student receives knowledge and training in the process of teaching and training becomes a person[7]. Sh.A.Cooperation with the student in the educational process of Amonashvili noting the need to establish his attitude, he says: "the student's training- knowledge activity is not only an interesting educational material and various methods of its explanation regulated by means, but also by the nature of the treatment of the educator in the educational process put. Student learning in an environment where there is affection, trust, cooperation, respect easily master his assignments[8]. High achievement, independent opinion, creative research the student who sees the assessment will receive more complex training assignments begins to strive to do". Both the use of problematic education in teaching and the use of creative abilities it is effective in shaping. A reality of readers

from educational techniques associated with independent search and discovery creative thinking of students along with heuristic or exploratory techniques the process that leads to the "laboratory" is also of fundamental importance[9].

Problem Education has several advantages in this regard:

1. It teaches students to think logically, scientifically, didactically, creatively.

2. He makes the teaching material convincing, by which knowledge can be attributed to faith promotes circulation.

3. He was generally much more influential, with deep intellectual feelings, including a high spirit, confidence in his own capabilities and strength of feeling it gives rise to the feeling, so it is of interest to readers, it makes up a serious interest in scientific knowledge in students.

4. Independent "discovery" of the law of truth is the knowledge gained forgetfulness has been clarified, independently generated knowledge has been forgotten even in the case, they can be quickly restored. Research on the problem is carried out on the educational process of students the attitude of the teacher and students to the correct Organization of the interaction process, selection and organization of educational materials, the process of mastering knowledge assessment system for improvement methods, training results showed dependence. Creativism and interoperability are strongly linked. in collaboration, creativity finds expression. Pedagogical creativism can only be defined by novelty should not be understood as the desire to conduct experiments. This aspiration is healthy also expresses the victory of thought over formality. Democracy, transparenc where it is not, in the course of the lesson with the administration and the will of the teacher creative cooperation in the development of independent thinking activities of students finds. Creative qobliyat of students in elementary school classes a special place is occupied by work on assignments that serve to develop.

Verbal, relying on life and learning experience in a comfortable environment for the student himself or, through his written speech, carries out the activity of thinking. Then ohar of a fan to actively cooperate with the teacher in relation to the edges unknown to himself spiritual preparation appears. It concerns questions posed on the subject tries to independently creative search for answers. Teacher in the process of such cooperation, together with the cultivation of student creativity also performs a diagnostic function, that is, the ability of students, the area of interest determines, champs creative talent. Tasks that develop creativism in the process of working on it, it is extremely important. Primary education is an education that leaves a deep mark on the life of every child being one of the types, at this stage of education, the educator has a great responsibility for teachers loaded. That is, the creativity skills of elementary students the development methodology still requires special study. Pupils do not become self-taught creatives. His creative ability it is formed through consistent reading and learning, working on oneself over a certain period of time, and gradually improving and developing. Teachers work in collaboration with students, giving each of their opinions by performing important tasks such as taking into account and making it noticeable to the reader achieving students to be creative i.e. with a different approach can. Teacher giving students problematic issues and situations[10], the creative approach of the reader to finding a solution to the issue is emotional volitional in it helps develop qualities. Working on these students, independent the opportunity to read and learn will be the impetus for an increase in inner need. The concept of "creativity" is associated with the concept of "creativity". However, "creativity" the concept did not find a worthy differentiation in the relevant dictionaries and creativity insufficiently defined in his psychology. In more than a dozen scientific works, the creativism of u or it is covered to different degrees, taking different approaches to the edges despite the fact that so far neither the problem itself nor the practical that applies to it there is no single stop to questions. Creativity and creativity, summarizing

the above points, are just one we came to the idea that the variety does not mean meaning. Because, when it comes to creativity, everyone has the invention, drawing, etc. of a certain thing can come to the eyes. But we have no creationism in our research, the task given in the course of the lesson [11]. Finding a path that is not like anyone and being able to scientifically substantiate it, thinking in a new way, making it we took it as the ability to take action. That is, in our research on the field of Education creativism refers to the creative abilities of elementary school students let's look at the development methodology. Creativity is broader than creativity we came to the idea that understanding.

Conclusion

Following the data observation, the following conclusions were developed:

- 1) first of all, to have clarity in the organization of each course process. Teacher should provide students with freedom, of course, in moderation;
- 2) one of the peculiarities of primary education is-children's the level of preparation for school, social experience, psychophysiological development are the same is not. According to elementary education in academic science programs attention to the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications in students in assignments although given, but the point of view of the development of creative activity in students- from the point of view it is necessary to improve them. That is, teachers are responsible and attentive it is necessary to be.

Also, when students' creative abilities are stimulated and sincere only when the environment is created can Creative Thinking become a habit. From error, to be afraid of successes, to focus on overestimation, there is a feeling of fear of being criticized in trainees creativism is a habit does not rotate.

- 3) certain factors creativity qualities in students, qualifications prevents development. Therefore, teachers in the pedagogical process they should focus on eliminating these factors. The following factors prevent the development of creativism in an individual:

- Self-risk withdrawal;
- Allowing rudeness in thinking and behavior;
- Personality fantasy and non-high assessment of tasvuri;
- Subject to others;
- In any case, just thinking about the achievement.
- David Lewis called creativism in children

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